

InterAcción y Perspectiv

Revista de Trabajo Social

ISSN 2244-808X
D.L. pp 201002Z43506

Enero-Junio 2024
Vol. 14 No. 1

Universidad del Zulia
Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Presentación de un modelo del rol de la educación superior en el desarrollo de empleos futuros. Estudio de caso: Universidad Integral de Ciencias Aplicadas/DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10277801

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Resumen

El propósito de este estudio es presentar un modelo del rol de la educación superior en el desarrollo de carreras futuras. Estudio de caso: Universidad de Ciencias Aplicadas. El método de investigación es mixto y la población estadística de esta investigación consta de dos grupos: el primer grupo de élites (incluidos gerentes industriales, responsables de políticas educativas de la Universidad de Ciencias Aplicadas y profesores de la Universidad de Ciencias Aplicadas) y el segundo grupo incluyó a estudiantes, egresados y profesores de una universidad integral de ciencias aplicadas. Se utilizó el método Delphi y el método de ecuaciones estructurales para presentar el modelo. Se diseñó una entrevista cualitativa, se seleccionaron dos escenarios de la Universidad Karafarin y la satisfacción de las necesidades de las comunidades locales como escenarios o perspectivas futuras de una universidad científico-aplicada integral. Luego, utilizando el método Delphi, se identificaron y extrajeron los enfoques educativos de las universidades para desarrollar las competencias requeridas para futuros empleos. Finalmente, se utilizó el modelo del rol de la educación superior en el desarrollo de empleos futuros utilizando el método de ecuaciones estructurales aprobado y ajustado.

Palabras clave: Educación superior, empleos futuros, delph, ecuaciones estructurales, universidad integral de ciencias aplicadas.

Abstract

Presentation of a Model of the Role of Higher Education in the Development of Future Jobs. Case Study: Comprehensive University of Applied Sciences.

The purpose of this study is to present a model of the role of higher education in the development of future careers. Case study: University of Applied Sciences. The research method is mixed, and the population for this research consists of two groups: the first group of elites (including industrial managers, responsible for educational policies at the University of Applied Sciences, and professors from the University of Applied Sciences), and the second group included students, graduates, and professors from a comprehensive university of applied sciences. The Delphi method and the structural equation modeling method were used to present the model. A qualitative interview was designed, and two scenarios—Karafarin University and meeting the needs of local communities—were selected as future perspectives of a comprehensive scientific-applied

university. Then, using the Delphi method, the educational approaches of universities were identified and extracted to develop the required competencies for future jobs. Finally, the model of the role of higher education in the development of future jobs was used, and the approved and adjusted structural equation modeling method was applied.

Key words: Higher education, future jobs, delphi, structural equations, comprehensive university of applied sciences.

Recibido: 30/08/23 Aceptado: 03/09/2023

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1.- Introduction

Social changes, technological advances and globalization are associated with new challenges that we must address. There is increasing individualism and increasing social diversity, along with increasing economic and cultural homogeneity (Richman, 2112). However, development and consolidation are necessary to cope with increasing complexity and uncertainty. Human skills and capabilities acquired through education, learning, and meaningful work are key drivers of economic success. Personal well-being and social cohesion. The future of global work is being transformed by a range of new technologies. Expansion, new sectors and markets, and the global economic system, more than any other period in history, are interconnected and largely determined by the information generated and popular quickly. However, over the past decade, with technological advances, massive job mobility, unsolvable skills shortages and competing claims about the unique nature of human intelligence Now challenged by artificial intelligence, the next decade will require determined leadership. to achieve a professional future that realizes human potential (Schwab and Zahidi, 2020).

Universities and higher education institutions, as the most important social institutions, play a fundamental role in social, economic, cultural and political development. Universities enjoy independence, self-governance and freedom. Scholars must feel responsible for the use of public, private, national and international resources. This means the company must constantly consider officials from other departments. Higher education is the most important form of investment in human resources by providing and enhancing the knowledge, attitudes and skills required by employees. They contribute to economic development in many different fields. The role and position of higher education in this era can become clearer if we pay attention to scientific predictions and estimates, changes and developments. They create speed in the field of

technology and therefore in the functioning of the economic institutions of the society (Fathi Vajargah, 2012). In the coming years we will see unemployment caused by the development of technology, that is why we can carry out activities and find new activities for the force labor (Julio, et al). The emergence of digital operating systems for online work is one of the changes in recent decades that will also affect businesses in the future. This not only concerns the models available on the market but also affects employment patterns. However, this problem can be seen as an opportunity and has created the conditions to make the most of this process. This technology offers the ability to work anywhere, anytime and will create any job (Janin Berg et al., 2113).

Another factor that requires preparation for the business and its future is flexibility. Greater business flexibility and more innovation should generate moderate growth in the economy, but this flexibility often results in the creation of few opportunities. Job security for qualified people is decreasing. Therefore, empowering employees in many ways is the basis for preparing businesses for the future. Additionally, readiness for change and acceptance of innovation is another factor in preparing for future work (Hosseininia, et al, 2020). The importance of university-industry collaboration for innovation and education has been widely recognized (Rybnicek & Königsgruber, 2019).

However, its importance increases as the economy faces increasingly competitive global markets for innovation and growth (Clauss & Kesting, 2015). Around the world, policymakers are emphasizing the importance of close ties between business and higher education as a tool for generating economic activity, investing significant sums of money. to encourage collaboration between universities and businesses (Brem & Radziwon, 2017). Therefore, although the importance of this issue has become clear over the past two decades, recognition of university-industry collaboration is essential for future economic and social prosperity. has never been mainstream in politics, management and academia. Ripoll Feliu and Díaz Rodríguez, 2017).

Hence the need for a future vision and a clear roadmap to continuously improve university-industry collaboration and maximize its benefits for all stakeholders, not just in policy and practice but also in the academic world, is becoming stronger than ever (Galan-Muros & Davey, 2018). The triple helix model was first introduced by Etzkowitz & Leydesdorf, describing the intersection between the three spirals, i.e., government, academia and industry creating new knowledge and stimulating innovation. The triple helix has become central to explaining the emergence of the knowledge

economy in policy and academic circles in recent decades (Etzkowitz, 1993). Furthermore, the literature on university-industry cooperation is based on its theoretical foundation.

In particular, the triple helix has reaffirmed the importance of universities, increased integration into the economy, and expanded the importance of knowledge for social development (Orazbayeva et al., 2019). This model proposes a “new position of the university,” in which the university occupies a broad and at least equal position with government and industry in creating and shaping the knowledge society., where public and private relations play a key role in improving national welfare. (Abramo et al., 2019). Universities add a third mission focusing on social and commercial engagement and entrepreneurship to the traditional primary missions of education and research. Recent developments have extended to four- and five-helix systems, including civil society and the environment (Carayannis et al., 2019). Orazbayeva et al. In 2019, the proposed future action plan on university-enterprise cooperation is presented in the table below

Table 1
The future practical plan for university-business cooperation
(Urazbayeva et al., 2013).

Strategies and approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empower scholars to make meaningful contributions to the industry. How time-dependent is this demand? • Ensure an open culture for collaboration between universities and businesses. How do the many stakeholders in the triangular spiral – government, academia and industry – foster such a culture in technology and other fields? • Create achievable goals, supported by a comprehensive and effective service system. How can a higher education institution deliver a single, easily achievable goal of corporate voting rights, with internal mechanisms, structures and organizational systems that ensure an organizational approach? Transparent, coordinated and inclusive? What flexibility is there for individual contributions within this framework? Configuration required? • Actively promote cooperation between universities and businesses. What is the best mechanism to promote university-enterprise cooperation at home and abroad in a triangular spiral? • Develop mechanisms to facilitate cooperation between universities and businesses. How do co-
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	<p>nominals extend across the triangular helix? What are the roles of different people in achieving this goal?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation in developing adaptive economic models. What innovative business models look like for organizations with university-industry collaborations and how to best communicate them to maximize the benefits of collaboration between universities and businesses? • Teaching suggestions for the future. How can the core curriculum be developed more flexibly to serve a more diverse community of lifelong learners?
<p>Entrepreneurship</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a broad business mindset. How can higher education institutions best develop an entrepreneurial spirit among staff and students? How to identify a change in psychology? • Encourage and promote business activities. How are university employees and students encouraged to take entrepreneurial action? Which methods have been most successful to date? How to achieve business change?
<p>participation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of participation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). What role do the actors of the triangular spiral play in the level of SME participation in higher education institutions? How is SMEs' willingness to participate in higher education institutions improved? What decisions do higher education institutions make to maximize Shared Value in their interactions with SMEs: How can policymakers support the scale of SME-based university-industry collaboration? • Communicate the potential benefits and forms of cooperation between universities and businesses with businesses and society. How can we best promote university-industry collaboration and its potential benefits for all businesses and communities? What are the best messages, message sources, and message channels for different target audiences? • Develop the workforce to achieve the best progress. How is recruitment and career development optimized to ensure the best possible workforce and encourage collaboration between universities and industry? • Improve stakeholder management. How can we improve the management of stakeholders and their expectations at the individual and organizational levels? • Integrate cooperation between universities and businesses in learning and teaching. How can

	<p>collaboration between universities and industry best be integrated through work-study training programs to promote student employability? Identify and overcome cultural differences that hinder progress. How to overcome cultural differences?</p>
<p>Context-based priority</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting university-business cooperation in economically weak areas. What are the best ways to strengthen university-business cooperation in multiple areas? Which form and mechanism should be used for university-business cooperation? • Considering national cultural differences in the design of support mechanisms. How can the learnings of other countries and cultures be adapted to other countries or regions? Which cultural factors are most relevant?

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

Education systems face the undeniable task of matching (and funding) competitive markets. limited or not yet fully trained. Concerns that formal education is too long, expensive and unsuited to the needs of a rapidly changing market are not new. At any given time, one-third of graduates are unemployed in fields unrelated to their jobs. As a result, higher education institutions increasingly need to collaborate with other stakeholders to address the skills gap (Klowden & Lim, 2021).

Unemployment among university graduates is one of the biggest economic problems in our country, the main axis of economic development and social progress. The university education system's lack of attention to society's needs is one of the causes of crisis and unemployment after graduation, while the basic need of university graduates is to find employment and acceptance of professional corporate responsibilities that are competencies; That is, in addition to intellectual, physical and educational abilities, as well as behavioral characteristics such as personality, attitude patterns, motivation and personal values, a person must also acquire technical skills. arts, people and cognition in their educational process. However, it is clear that there has not been a logical balance between school training courses and what marketers require in terms of scientific and technical skills, on the other hand, before students graduate, there are no suitable criteria. appropriate to evaluate them technically. Minimum scientific and practical capacity. Furthermore, the education system has not been able to enhance the scientific spirit of students so that they can find useful jobs for

themselves and society (Entezirian, 2012). One of the requirements for the policy of the education sector is to create a quality education system and identify the current and future trends of the labor market in the country and at the international level; So that in the past decade, special attention has been paid to the fields of study in advanced countries and the ability of the graduates to provide services has been observed (Dadandish, 2019).

Currently, there is no logical link between the education system and the domestic labor market, both in terms of quality and quantity, and for this reason it is necessary to establish coordination between the higher education system suitable for students. graduates and the labor market system to avoid waste. resources. Therefore, in the meantime, considering the position of universities of applied sciences, established with the aim of raising the level of competence of workers in economic sectors and improving professional skills of graduates of teaching centers lacking leadership experience, is becoming a matter of concern. increasingly important. No longer needed. Based on the information obtained, it is possible to determine the composition and behavior of various future tasks, and to plan and implement practical solutions to address them in sufficient time before performance. event and from the results obtained, they can be used as a sign. and advice. Those who go to school, study, and find jobs are accustomed to the education that society requires and prevents them from moving into saturated jobs.

The University of General Applied Sciences is a job-oriented university, meaning the majors are determined by the jobs in this school and these majors meet the needs of jobs and occupations. However, we can say that the University of Applied Sciences is in some ways closer to the third-generation universities that are entrepreneurial universities. Turning science into wealth and creating prosperity in society is the most important indicator of third-generation universities. Turning science into wealth means that technology transfer and sales will take place and third-generation college graduates will be able to use the knowledge they gain to train scientists. study and create jobs in society. Considering the large gap between the existing number of jobs in the country and the identified jobs in the world, one of the projects of the school is to introduce new jobs to the society in the new era and identify them. from academic fields. Train and introduce these people into the job market.

2.- Research background

In this section, a number of researches related to the topic of research outside and inside Iran have been reviewed based on their goals, techniques used and their achievements

Table 2.
Background of the research

Internal investigation background		
Darabi et al	2019	Investigating the future changes of work in Iran with an emphasis on the opportunities and challenges of jobs in the framework of Iran's territorial planning (Iran's labor market forecast in the horizon of 1421 AH)
Jamshidi et al	2019	Solutions for the development of knowledge-based employment in the country based on the Foundation's data method
Heydarieh and Ahangar	2018	The future of market research of start-up businesses in Iran
Golkar	2018	Future study of socio-cultural consequences of the "work in the future" phenomenon.
Abdolshad et al	2017	Xompilation and selection of university management strategies using the blue ocean approach (case study: applied science university)
Bagheri et al	2017	Designing a model for measuring the effectiveness of government organizational universities (case study: Scientific and Applied Center of Telecommunications Factories of Iran)
Kemari et al	2016	Designing a strategic thinking model for the administrators of a comprehensive university of applied sciences
Moradi and Delshad	2016	Examining the relationship between vocational training courses and employment and entrepreneurship; (Study by the graduates of Bandarlangheh University of Applied Sciences)
Mohammadi et al	2014	Evaluation of the courses of the Comprehensive Applied Science University based on the needs assessment of the labor market
Moradi Dehaghi	2013	Evaluation of the success of applied scientific university courses in promoting public awareness Career from the point of view of students and professors and their comparison
External research background		

Paul et al	2019	Towards responsible entrepreneurship education and the future of the workforce
Urazbayeva et al	2019	The future of university-business collaboration: priorities for research and practice
Minooka et al	2018	Developing a future-ready global workforce: a case study from a top UK university
Holmes and Marcus	2018	Education and labor market outcomes
Marques-Ramos and Morele	2016	Choosing an appropriate approach to analyze the future of higher education
Rissart et al	2016	From foresight to impact? Future work scenarios in 2030
Rickman	2012	Higher education in the future: which key skills should be promoted through university teaching and learning?
Balls et al	2010	Outlook: The future of the higher education sector in England

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

3. Research methods

The current study is mixed methods (qualitative-quantitative). Mixed methods research is carried out by choosing appropriate qualitative and quantitative research methods and their optimal combination. Thus, between the research subjects, their data collection and analysis methods, and for the respondents, the necessary compatibility is established with the research questions. In this case, in addition to having measurable aspects of the phenomenon under study, other aspects of the phenomenon are also considered. Regarding research purposes, research is divided into 3 types (Bazargan, 1983).

This research will take place in two phases, the first phase is development and the second phase is application. Because in the first phase we seek to define the educational methods of a comprehensive university of applied sciences aimed at developing the skills necessary to perform the jobs of the future and in the In the second paragraph, we seek to use it to provide a model that explains the role of higher education and, thus, of being a comprehensive university of applied sciences in the development of future employment. Qualitative data were collected using Delphi questionnaires and expert interviews. The expert community includes industrial managers, educational policy makers of the University of Applied Sciences and professors of the University of

Applied Sciences. In the quantitative part, the statistical subjects of the study included students, graduates and professors of the University of Applied Sciences and a quantitative questionnaire with 5 Likert options was used to collect data. quantitative data.

4. Process of conducting research

First step:

As with other methods, identify and specify the desired topic and define the analysis period. For example, the main topic might be the future of work in 1410.

Second step:

Identify desired scenarios:

In this step, two to three desired scenarios are selected through the environmental scanning method to present a model of the role of higher education (universities) in future employment development and the case study is Comprehensive University of Applied Sciences. Therefore, by examining the scenarios related to the future of the universities, two scenarios of entrepreneurial university and meeting the needs of local communities were selected by the 2017 Foresight Working Group. It should be noted that the two scenarios that are closely related to national documents are as following Figure.

Figure 1. Two scenarios

The third step:

In this step, the educational approaches of the universities for the development of competencies were identified using the Delphi method (2 to 9 rounds).

Step 4:

In this step, using a quantitative questionnaire tool, the model of the role of higher education of universities in the development of the future jobs under study was presented: comprehensive scientific-applied university.

5. Data analysis and research findings

5.1. Identification of desirable scenarios of landscape creation through environmental scanning to formulate a qualitative questionnaire

In this part of the current research, in order to compile a qualitative questionnaire by examining scenarios related to the future of universities, after interviewing experts in the field of higher education and industry, two scenarios of entrepreneurial universities and meeting the needs of local communities were selected. In the entrepreneurial university scenario, universities have a market-oriented approach to operations without losing the core academic values.

The university's three missions, which are teaching, research, and social service, are well balanced, although there is great differentiation among institutions, which results from high independence and greater responsibility. Business perspectives to international markets and e-learning are important. University resources and academic staff salaries and credit have improved. Connections to the local economy are strong. In the second alternative scenario, i.e., meeting the needs of local communities, higher education institutions are focused on national and local missions. They are represented in regional and local associations, and are intended to respond to local and domestic social and economic needs regarding education and research. Higher education is basically financed and administered by the government. Academics have control over the teaching and research process. Few prominent higher education institutions and research departments have been able to connect to international networks at the same time. Although now there are obstacles to internationalization (maintain their high national status).

In general, higher education institutions focus on education and research based on the needs of local and regional communities. International associations and businesses are eager to support local institutions. Also, retraining courses create benefits. Universities and industrial colleges have the same position, and universities have a smaller role in research than in the past. Both types of educational and research institutes have become increasingly connected to industry, providing continuing education as well as the introductory training they need. The scope of academic research has decreased to some extent. While research is developed in the public sector. Research in strategic fields such as physics or engineering has been transferred to the government sector, and international joint research continues with a limited number of friendly

countries. University researchers are focused on humanities and social sciences, two valuable areas to support national culture. Academics continue to do research, but education is their primary goal.

5.2. Identifying the educational approaches of the comprehensive scientific-applied university for the development of competencies according to the desired perspective of the entrepreneurial university and meeting local needs.

At this stage, using the Delphi method (open questionnaire), the experts were asked what educational approaches the University of Applied Sciences should consider for the development of competencies, considering the vision of the entrepreneurial university and meeting local needs. The results of the second round of Delphi It is as described in the table below.

Table 3. Counting results of the second stage of the survey (the second round of Delphi)

		Degree of agreement	very little	Low	somewhat	Much	very much	Level
1	Supporting entrepreneurial behaviors	0		0	0	8	4	%17
2	Support teamwork	0		1	0	4	5	%17
3	Strengthening participation	0		0	2	8	2	%84
4	Strengthen new ideas	1		0	1	7	3	%84
5	Supporting new ideas	0		1	2	5	4	%80
6	Valuing innovation	0		0	4	2	4	%17
7	Decentralization	1		0	3	4	2	%84
8	Fulfilling the entrepreneurial mission	0		0	0	4	8	%100
9	Developing a common vision	0		0	3	3	4	%17
10	Entrepreneurial knowledge	0		1	1	5	5	%74
11	Communication with schools	0		0	3	5	7	%77

12	Development of interdisciplinary curricula	0	0	1	8	3	%88
13	Needs assessment at regional and national level	0	0	1	4	5	%89
14	Business strategy	2	0	4	5	2	%84
15	Creating scientific and technological development centers for scientific and applied universities	2	1	1	4	4	%47
16	Reforming the university research system	1	2	1	7	1	%47
17	Modifying course headings	0	0	0	5	5	%100
18	Designing a collaborative approach with the participation of entrepreneurs	0	0	0	5	7	%100
19	Support and cooperation with academic entrepreneurs	0	0	3	4	4	%84
20	Strengthening the office of communication with the industry	0	0	0	4	8	%88
21	Establishing a quality committee at the university level	0	0	3	3	4	%75
22	Commercialization of research results	0	0	3	4	4	%84
23	Entrepreneurial leadership	0	2	2	2	5	%37

24	Knowledge transfer and communication technology with universities in developed countries	0	0	0	2	4	%100
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Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

As per the consequences of the second round of Delphi, which shows that in regards to the over 24 qualities, the understanding of the specialists is 70%, and the aftereffects of the twofold adjusts of the execution of the Delphi technique in the examination show that, for the accompanying reasons, an agreement was reached among the individuals from the factual example and can be rehashed. Adjusts finished. In the subsequent round, over 67% of the individuals picked the elements for the instructive methodologies of the Exhaustive Logical Applied College for the improvement of skills, which had a normal more prominent than 3, among their thought about factors. This coordination coefficient for individuals' responses about the request for factors in the subsequent round is 0.619. Because of the way that the quantity of test individuals was in excess of ten individuals, this measure of Kendall's coefficient is viewed as very critical. Kendall's coordination coefficient for the plan of the powerful figures the instructive methodologies of the exhaustive logical applied college for the improvement of capabilities, in the subsequent round contrasted with the principal round, just expanded by 41%. has had consideration.

5.3. Show of the model of the job of advanced education of colleges (in the improvement of future positions under study: complete logical applied college

In this piece of the examination, utilizing primary condition investigation, we present a model of the job of advanced education of colleges in the improvement of future positions under study: complete logical applied college, whose factors are among the pointers extricated from the Delphi technique to distinguish instructive methodologies of colleges to foster skills with Regard for the requirements of future positions (counting; Understanding the mission of business venture, changing the educational program, planning cooperative methodologies with the support of business visionaries, moving information and innovation, and associating with colleges in created nations have been removed.

5.3.1. Analyzing the exploration model on account of standard coefficients

Figure 2. Analyzing the exploration model

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

5.3.2. Examining the research model in the case of significant numbers

Figure 3. Examining the research model

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

The above figure shows the test of the research model (the mode of significant coefficients). Using this test, you can understand the significance of the relationship between the research variables. The results table of the effects of the model variables is reported in the table below.

Table 4. Path analysis results of the research model

	Path coefficient	t statistic	Significance of the path
Transfer of knowledge → correction	0,082	0,853	0,934
Knowledge transfer → realization of entrepreneurial mission	0,465	6,070	0,000
Knowledge transfer*participation→correction	0,157	6,000	0,000
Corrections→ Fulfillment of the entrepreneurial mission	0,506	6,544	0,000
Improvement → development of future jobs	0,491	4,583	0,000
Fulfilling the mission of entrepreneurship → developing future jobs	0,478	4,447	0,000

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

6. Conclusions

The issue of business and getting individuals to the ideal occupation is one of the most essential necessities of a general public. Joblessness has been examined as a horrendous social, monetary, and social peculiarity, and its answer has forever been one of the essential worries of legislators. The financial advancement interaction of every nation at last decides its HR. In such manner, the full and fitting utilization of HR of every nation ought to be thought of as one of the essential objectives of advancement. For this reason, various legislatures are attempting to give admittance to scholarly and expertise preparing for individuals of their general public and set them up for working in various positions.

Meanwhile, a significant issue that needs exceptional consideration is that the idea of occupations later on will be not the same as the present because of patterns and changes at the degree of society. Hence, it can't be anticipated that the HR who have been prepared to assume a part in past positions, can possibly assume a part in new

and arising position from here on out. It is very evident that the absence of planning to manage the wide changes representing things to come work market and the absence of arrangement of HR to perform future positions will prompt broad joblessness in various social orders. Later on, it will prompt inescapable social, financial, political, and different issues and difficulties. In this way, numerous organizations at the public and worldwide level have explored and distinguished the ground-breaking patterns representing things to come and their effect on positions from here on out.

Like different nations on the planet, the work market in Iran will be impacted by future patterns and advancements. Nonetheless, starter examinations demonstrate that college and ability stages of preparation are not given in view representing things to come requirements of the work market. In such manner, the assessment of the aftereffects of workforce measurements shows the peculiarity It is somewhat uncommon in the market of the country. A peculiarity that might be alluded to as "reversal of the work market". A circumstance where the joblessness pace of college graduates is far higher than the overall joblessness rate in the general public. As a matter of fact, this peculiarity shows that college graduates have less possibility of work contrasted with different segments of the general public.

This is in spite of the way that in most evolved nations of the world, college graduates have a lower joblessness rate than the overall joblessness rate. One of the fundamental explanations behind this issue is the failure of the advanced education framework, or all in all, the confuse between advanced education and the work market. Truth be told, the absence of association between college courses and the necessities of the country's economy has become one of the serious emergencies of the public authority as of late. It ought to be noticed that the continuation of this cycle from now on (the absence of suitability of training with the necessities of the work market) will make us face a lot of taught HR who, from one viewpoint, don't have what it takes and mastery expected for future positions, and then again, are They are not going about responsibilities inconsequential to their field of study.

This disparity in the end prompts broad joblessness in the public arena, trip of elites and loss of human resources, social imbalance, conduct irregularities, sorrow of HR, and so on in the public arena. Taking into account the outcomes of proceeding with the ongoing system of training in the country without focusing on the abilities and specializations required for future positions, it is important to lead concentrates on future positions and the abilities and specializations they need in the nation and to change the

country's instructive projects as per them. In this manner, meanwhile, analyzing the place of the applied logical college, which was made determined to build the expertise level of laborers in different financial areas and expanding the expert abilities of alumni of instructive focuses that need leader experience, turns out to be increasingly fundamental.

The aftereffects of the exploration showed that to answer the necessities of future positions, the applied complete college ought to have approaches that incorporate; Understanding the mission of business venture, changing the educational plan, planning cooperative methodologies with the support of business people, moving information and innovation and associating with colleges in created nations, and utilizing these ways to deal with model the job of advanced education (colleges) in the improvement of future positions. Study: A Far reaching Logical Applied College was introduced, and by utilizing its outcomes, one can make a stride towards understanding the mission of advanced education, particularly a Thorough Logical Applied College, and working on the current circumstances.

7. Recommendations

7.1. common-sense ideas

- ✓ It is recommended that the public authority offer the important help to make information-based organizations and organizations
- ✓ It is recommended to understand the pioneering college in the extensive logical applied college which is the mission the central thing of this college is that arranging ought to be finished.
- ✓ It is recommended that boards under the title of value improvement of applied logical college communities ought to be laid out in each instructive gathering and the referenced aspects, parts and pointers ought to be refined and refreshed like clockwork.
- ✓ It is recommended that as a data set of execution marks of universities and specialized schools and callings, the assessments of specialists in this field are gotten through a virtual framework and persistent improvement is finished.
- ✓ It is proposed that all degrees of administrators of applied logical colleges, including division heads, heads of resources, and college presidents, ought to be cleared up for the hypothetical premise of scholastic business.

7.2. Ideas for future examination

- ✓ Estimating the condition of the applied logical college with a situation composing approach;

- ✓ Involving the fluffy underlying examination strategy to recognize future patterns influencing position;
- ✓ Looking at the way of behaving of key entertainers in the field of advanced education in the country with the viewpoint school approach;
- ✓ Determining future positions in different businesses like horticulture and medication.

Bibliographic references

- Entezirian, Nahid and Tahmasabi, Tahereh. (2012). Examining the level of coordination and adaptation of the higher education system and Technical and professional training with the needs of the labor market. **work and society**. No. 141.
- Bazargan Harandi, Abbas. (2000). **Introduction to qualitative and mixed research methods: common approaches in Behavioral Sciences**. Didar Publication.
- Hosseininia, Gholam Hossein and Bakhtiari, Marzieh. (2020). The future of the labor market and leadership in future jobs. The first international conference on new challenges and solutions in industrial engineering and management and accounting. Sari. <https://civilica.com/doc/1045363>.
- Dadandish, P. and Rahnavard, H. (2019). The effect of quality education on the employment and personal identity of young people. **Studies Sports and youth strategy** 18 (44).
- Abdi Hamid, Mirshah Jafari Ibrahim, Nili Mohammad Reza, Rajaipour Saeed. (2017). explanation of the horizon of 1414 Iran's higher education using scenario writing method. Iran's higher education. **Period** 3 No. 1-4:27.
- Eisazadeh Saeed and Hosseini Saeedeh Alsadat. (2012). study of the effects of trade with China on the employment sector Iran Industry. **Economic Research Journal**. Volume 14 1 Number 55 From page 115 to page 191.
- Fathi Vajargah, Korosh and Khosravi, Mahbobeh. (2012). **Acceptance of innovation in higher education curriculum**. Tehran: Personality Publications.
- Fathi Vajargah. (2007). **The strategic transformation plan of the country's science and technology** (global scenarios report). Science and Technology, Scientific Policy Research Center of the country. research plan.
- Karbasi, Alireza; Ezni Ashari, Hajar and Aghil, Hassan. (2007). Forecasting the employment of the agricultural sector in Iran. **Economy and agricultural development** (agricultural sciences and industries). volume 22. number 2. from pages 31 to 43.
- Klowden, Kevin & Lim, Quintus. (2021). **Future of work: Insights for 2021 and Beyond**. Report of milken institute.
- Schwab, Klaus & Zahidi, Saadia. (2020). The Future of Jobs Report. The World Economic Forum. Published: 20 October 2020.
- Rieckmann, Marco. (2012). Future-oriented higher education: Which key competencies should be fostered through university teaching and learning. Volume 44. Issue 2. March 2012. Pages 127-135.
- Julio C. Canedo, George Graen, Miriam Grace. (2018). Let's make performance management work for new hires: **They are the future**. **Organizational Dynamics**. Volume 47. Issue 4. Pages 229-233.

- Janine Berg., arianne Furrer, Ellie Harmon., Uma Rani., M Six Silberman. (2019). **Digital labour platforms and the future of work: Towards decent work in the online world** International Labour Office – Geneva. ILO.
- Rybnicek, R., Königsgruber, R.(2019). What makes industry–university collaboration succeed. **A systematic review of the literature. Journal of Business Economics** 89(2).221–250.
- Clauss, T., Kesting, T., (2017). How businesses should govern knowledge intensive collaborations with universities: An empirical investigation of university professors. *Industrial Marketing Management* 62. 185–198.
- Sarpong, D., AbdRazak, A., Alexander, E., et al. (2015). Organizing practices of university. industry and government that facilitate (or impede) the transition to a hybrid triple helix model of innovation. **Technological Forecasting and Social Change** 123, 142–152.
- Brem, A., Radziwon, A. (2017). Efficient Triple Helix collaboration fostering local niche innovation projects–A case from Denmark. **Technological Forecasting and Social Change** 123, 130–141.
- Quintana, C.D.D., J-G, Mora, Pérez, P.J., et al. (2016). Enhancing the development of competencies: The role of UBC. **European Journal of Education** 51 (1).10–24.
- Ripoll Feliu, V., Díaz Rodríguez, A. (2017). Knowledge transfer and university-business relations: Current trends in research. **Intangible Capital** 13 (4).697–719.
- Galan-Muros, V., Davey, T. (2017). The UBC ecosystem: Putting together a comprehensive framework for university-business cooperation. **The Journal of Technology Transfer** 42 (2), 1–36.
- Mascarenhas, C., Ferreira, J.J., Marques, C. (2018). University–industry cooperation: A systematic literature review and research agenda. **Science and Public Policy** 45 (5). 708–718.
- Etzkowitz, H. (1993). Enterprises from science: The origins of science-based regional economic development. **Minerva** 31 (3).326–360.
- Etzkowitz, H., Leydesdorff, L. (1995). The Triple Helix–University-industrygovernment relations: A laboratory for knowledge based economic development. **EASST Review** 14 (1). 4–9.
- Nyman, G.S. (2015). University-business-government collaboration: From institutes to platforms and ecosystems. **Triple Helix** 2 (2), 1–20.
- Hladchenko, M., Pinheiro, R. (2019). Implementing the Triple Helix Model: Means-Ends Decoupling at the State Level? **Minerva** 57 (1). 1–22.
- Abramo, G., D’Angelo, C.A., Solazzi, M. (2012). A bibliometric tool to assess the regional dimension of university–industry research collaborations. *Scientometrics* 91(3), 955–975.
- Orazbayeva, B., Plewa, C., Davey,T., Galan Muros, V.(2019). The Future of University-Business Cooperation: Research and Practice Priorities. **Journal of Engineering and Technology Management**. Volume 54. Pages 67- 80.
- Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017). The future of employment: how susceptible are jobs to computerisation? *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. 114, 254-280.
- Davies, A., Fidler, D., & Gorbis, M. (2011). Future work skills 2020. Institute for the Future for University of Phoenix Research Institute. 540. 31.WEF. (2016a). The future of jobs: Employment, skills and workforce strategy for the fourth industrial revolution: World Economic Forum. Geneva. Switzerland.